

BILAGA 5.2 Frågeformulär för MaMi på engelska.

Part 1: During pregnancy: week 17-19
Part 2: During pregnancy: week 28-30
Part 3: After delivery: 6-10 weeks after estimated date of birth

Section 1. Background questions (Part 1)
Section 2. Questions about the pregnancy and gynaecological health (Part 1)
Section 3. General questions about health (Part 1-2)
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Section 5. General questions about health after pregnancy (Part 3)
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(Web-based questionnaire)

MaMi

The Swedish Maternal Microbiome Project:
Questionnaire to study participants **Part 1-2**

Date: _____
E-mail: _____
Please repeat e-mail: _____
Phone: _____

Please enter your personal identity number (12 digits: yyyyymmdd-xxxx): _____

MaMi

The Swedish Maternal Microbiome Project:
Questionnaire to study participants **Part 3**

Date: _____
E-mail: _____
Please repeat e-mail: _____
Phone: _____

Please enter your personal identity number (12 digits: yyyyymmdd-xxxx): _____

We would like to follow up on the health of the children of the women who participated in this study. We would therefore appreciate if you could enter the personal identity number of your child, if you approve that we follow up the child's well-being and possible diseases.

(12 digits: yyyyymmdd-xxxx): _____

1. Background questions (Part 1)

What year were you born (yyyy)? _____
How tall are you (cm)? _____
What was your weight before you got pregnant (kg)? _____
What country were you born in?

Sweden
 Outside of Sweden (please state which country): _____

Family

Partner (married, cohabitation or living-apart)
 Single

Do you already have children?

- No
- Yes, biological child/children (number of children _____)
- Yes, adopted child/children and/or stepchild/stepchildren (number of children _____)

How many children do you have that attend pre-school/kindergarten (number of children)? _____

What is your highest level of completed education?

Primary school Senior high school / Upper secondary school
 University/collage Other

What was your working situation like before you got pregnant?

- Worked full-time
- Worked part-time
- Long-term sick listed (more than 3 months)
- Unemployed/looking for employment
- Student
- Other: _____

Are you in contact with animals during your work or spare time?

No yes
 If yes, please state which animal/animals: dog, cat, rabbit, rodent, reptile, horse, cow, sheep, pig, chicken, other: _____

Have you been abroad the last 3 months? Yes/ no

If so, which country/countries have you been to the last 3 months? _____

2. Questions about the pregnancy and gynaecological health (Part 1)

What pregnancy-week are you currently in? _____

When is your estimated date of delivery? _____

What is your weight today (kg)? _____

Are you expecting more than one child (twins, triplets etc.)? Yes/no/don't know

For how long have you tried to get pregnant (months)? _____

How did you become pregnant? Please tick all applicable alternatives for conception:

- Natural conception (coitus)
- Medical treatment / ovulation stimulation/induction (e.g. hormone injections, Clomiphene, Metformin)
- Surgical treatment needed (e.g. surgery for endometriosis)
- Assisted reproduction: insemination
- Assisted reproduction: in vitro fertilization (IVF)
- Assisted reproduction: intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI)
- Fertility treatment of the father

Is this your first pregnancy? Yes/no

If no:

How many times have you been pregnant before (excluding the current pregnancy)? _____

How many children have you given birth to? _____

How many early miscarriages have you had (before 16 weeks)? _____

Has any child you were expecting died during the pregnancy after week 16 (late miscarriage or intrauterine foetal death)? _____

Comment: _____

How many sexual partners have you had intercourse with during the last year?

- None
- 1
- 2-10
- 11-20
- More than 20
- Prefer not to answer
-

Questions about your menstruation (when not on hormonal contraceptives/intrauterine device/pregnant):

If you have pains during menstruation, how discomforting are your pains on a scale from 0-10 (0 = no pain and 10 = severe, disabling pain)? _____

Do you use analgesic/pain killers during your menstruation? Yes/no

Do you experience pain linked to/during ovulation? Yes/no

Do you have regular menstruation? Yes (approx. 28 days), no (≥ 35 days), no (less than 6 times/year), no (less than 3 times/year)

How many days is your average menstrual cycle, from the first day of one period to the first day of the next? State in days: _____

Do your menstruations usually start with smaller bleeding for over two days before the proper bleeding starts? Yes/no (If yes, small bleeding for how many days: _____)

Supplementary questions:

Have you had the diagnosis endometriosis? Yes, diagnosis without surgery/ yes, diagnosis following surgery/no/don't know.

Have you at any time been diagnosed with PCOS (Polycystic Ovary Syndrome)?

Yes/no/don't know.

Have you had acne as an adult? No/ yes, no treatment / yes, local treatment/ yes, antibiotic treatment.

Do you experience problems with thin hair on the top of your head (see picture)?

- No problem with thin hair
- Type 1 according to Ludwig Scale
- Type 2 according to Ludwig Scale
- Type 3 according to Ludwig Scale

Do you experience disturbing body hair? Yes/ no
If yes, please sum up the points according to the pictures below: Score. Total points: _____ (between 0-36 points)

Questions about screening for cervical cancer (pap smear test or cell specimens): (yes/no/don't know)

- Have you ever participated in testing of gynaecological pap smear: (for screening of cervical cancer)?
- Have you regularly gone for testing of gynaecological pap smear when summoned?
- Have you at any time had an abnormal HPV-test (Human Papilloma Virus)?
- Have you at any time had cell changes at the gynaecological pap smear?
- Have you at any time undergone biopsy (tissue sampling) from the cervix?
- Have you previously undergone a loop electrical excision procedure (removing a small part of the cervix as treatment of cell changes)?
- Are you vaccinated against HPV (t. ex Gardasil/Silgard/Cervarix)

Have you had any gynaecological infection in the last 3 months? Yes/no/don't know.

If yes, which infection/infections have you had?

- Chlamydia
- Gonorrhoea
- Bacterial vaginosis
- Genital herpes
- *Mycoplasma genitalium*
- Vaginal yeast infection/vaginal thrush
- Condyloma
- Trichomoniasis (*Trichomonas vaginalis*)
- Other. If other, which other gynaecological infection have you had in the last 3 months? _____

Have you used any contraceptives the last year before you got pregnant? Yes/no

If yes, which contraceptive/contraceptives have you used in the last year?

- Birth control pills (including mini-pills)
- Birth control shot (hormone injection every 3 months)
- Birth control implant
- Vaginal hormonal ring
- Copper IUD = Intrauterine device/ coil
- Hormonal IUD = Intrauterine device/ coil
- Condom
- Pessary /diaphragm
- Natural family planning (t. ex: safe periods)
- Other: _____

3. General questions about health (Part 1)

How do you rate your general state of health?

- Very good
 Good
 Neither good or bad
 Poor
 Very poor

Have you at any time used antibiotics during the last three months BEFORE you got pregnant? Yes/no

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you used antibiotics in the 3 months BEFORE pregnancy?

- Respiratory tract infection (pneumonia, sinusitis)
- Tonsillitis
- Otitis
- Urinary tract infection
- Skin and soft tissue infection (skin, muscles, sore)
- Intestinal infection (bacteria, e.g. salmonella or campylobacter, parasites or traveller's diarrhoea)
- Abdominal infection (e.g. appendicitis, cholecystitis, diverticulitis)
- Gynaecological infection (e.g. chlamydia, gonorrhoea, bacterial vaginosis)
- Other: _____

Have you used antibiotics at any time DURING this pregnancy? Yes/no

If yes, at what week/weeks of pregnancy: _____

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you used antibiotics DURING this pregnancy?

- Respiratory tract infection (pneumonia, sinusitis)
- Tonsillitis
- Otitis
- Urinary tract infection
- Skin and soft tissue infection (skin, muscles, sore)
- Intestinal infection (bacteria, e.g. salmonella or campylobacter, parasites or traveller's diarrhoea)
- Abdominal infection (e.g. appendicitis, cholecystitis, diverticulitis)
- Gynaecological infection (e.g. chlamydia, gonorrhoea, bacterial vaginosis)
- Other: _____

Have you been to the dentist/ dental hygienist DURING the last 3 months before you got pregnant? Yes/no.

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you been to the dentist/dental hygienist DURING the last 3 months before you got pregnant? _____

Have you been to the dentist/dental hygienist so far DURING this pregnancy? Yes/no.

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you been to the dentist/dental hygienist DURING this pregnancy? _____

Do you smoke/ have you smoked?

- No, I have never smoked.
 Yes, I did smoke earlier.

Yes, I smoke now.

Other smoking habits

If you used to smoke, what year did you stop? _____

If you smoke, how many cigarettes do you now smoke a day? <1, 1-5, 6-10, >10

What other habits of smoking do you have? _____

Do you use "snus" /have you used "snus"?

No, I have never used snus.

Yes, did use snus earlier.

Yes, use snus now.

Other habits of using snus

If you used to use snus, what year did you stop? _____

How many snus do you now take each day? <1, 1-5, 6-10, >10

What other habits of snus do you have? _____

How often did you have a drink containing alcoholic during the last three months BEFORE you got pregnant?

- Never
- Monthly or less
- 2 to 4 times a month
- 2 to 3 times a week
- 4 or more times a week

How many drinks containing alcohol did you have a typical day when you were drinking during the last three months BEFORE you got pregnant?

- 1 or 2
- 3 or 4
- 5 or 6
- 7, 8 or 9
- 10 or more
-

How often did you have a drink containing alcoholic DURING this pregnancy?

- Never
- Monthly or less
- 2 to 4 times a month
- 2 to 3 times a week
- 4 or more times a week

How many drinks containing alcohol do you have a typical day when you are drinking DURING this pregnancy?

- 1 or 2
- 3 or 4
- 5 or 6
- 7, 8 or 9
- 10 or more

Have you received treatment for any of the following diseases (prior to pregnancy)?

Yes/no/don't know

- Diabetes
 - o Type 1
 - o Type 2
- Thyroid disease

- o Overactive thyroid (hyperthyroidism)
- o Underactive thyroid (hypothyroidism, treated with e.g. Levaxin)
- High blood pressure (hypertension)
- Cancer treated with chemotherapy, radiotherapy or hormone therapy.
- Multiple sclerosis (MS)
- Rheumatism or other autoimmune diseases (e.g. SLE or scleroderma)
- Crohn's disease
- Ulcerative colitis
- Allergy
 - o Asthma
 - o Eczema
 - o Hay fever/Allergic rhinitis
 - o Other allergy
- Other disease, please explain which disease: _____

Has a doctor or other healthcare professional ever told you that you might have an eating disorder? Yes/no/don't know

If yes, when a doctor or other healthcare professional told you that you might have an eating disorder, which eating disorder did they say you have (please mark all relevant):

- a. Anorexia
- b. Bulimia
- c. Binge eating disorder
- d. Other specified or unspecified eating disorder
- e. Other eating disorder _____

Have any of your biological parents, siblings or children ever had an eating disorder?
Yes/no/don't know

So far during this pregnancy, do you have or have you had any complications/ medical problems?

What pregnancy-related complications have you experienced during this pregnancy?
(Yes/no/don't know)

- Gestational diabetes
- Thyroid disease
 - o Overactive thyroid (hyperthyroidism)
 - o Underactive thyroid (hypothyroidism, treated with e.g. Levaxin)
- High blood pressure (hypertension) (that you did not have before pregnancy)
- Pre-eclampsia (toxaemia)
- Hyperemesis gravidarum (severe morning sickness)
- Depression
- Vaginal bleeding/threatened abortion
- Heartburn/dyspepsia
- Symphysis pubis dysfunction/ pelvic girdle pain
- Other

If other, please describe which _____

Did you take any medications regularly before you got pregnant? Yes/no

If yes, what medications did you take regularly before you got pregnant?

- Non-prescription/over-the-counter analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Alvedon, Ipren)
- Opioids, stronger analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Morfin, Oxynorm)
- Allergy medications (e.g. antihistamines like Aeries, Loratidin)
- Asthma medications (e.g. Inhalations like Bricanyl, Pulmicort, Ventoline)
- Antidepressant medications (e.g. Citalopram, Sertralin)

- Sedative and anti-anxiety agents (e.g. Sobril, Stesolid)
 - Hypnotics/sleeping pills (e.g. Imovane, Propavan)
 - Thyroid hormone (e.g. Levaxin)
 - Antihypertensive/blood pressure medications (e.g. Enalapril, Furix, Lasix, Spironolaktin, Amlodipin, Felodipin, Atacand, Losartan, Seloken, Metoprolol)
 - Medications decreasing the gastric acid production (e.g. Proton-pump-inhibitors like Omeprazol or similar)
 - Other
- What other medications did you take regularly before you got pregnant? _____

Do you take any medications regularly since you got pregnant? Yes/no

If yes, what medications do you take regularly since you got pregnant?

- Non-prescription/over-the-counter analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Alvedon, Ipren)
 - Opioids, stronger analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Morfin, Oxynorm)
 - Allergy medications (e.g. antihistamines like Aeries, Loratidin)
 - Asthma medications (e.g. Inhalations like Bricanyl, Pulmicort, Ventoline)
 - Antidepressant medications (e.g. Citalopram, Sertralin)
 - Sedative and anti-anxiety agents (e.g. Sobril, Stesolid)
 - Hypnotics/sleeping pills (e.g. Imovane, Propavan)
 - Thyroid hormone (e.g. Levaxin)
 - Antihypertensive/blood pressure medications (e.g. Enalapril, Furix, Lasix, Spironolaktin, Amlodipin, Felodipin, Atacand, Losartan, Seloken, Metoprolol)
 - Medications decreasing the gastric acid production (e.g. Proton-pump-inhibitors like Omeprazol or similar)
 - Other
- What other medications did you take regularly since you got pregnant? _____

In the last 24 hours, for how long have you felt nauseated or sick to your stomach?

- Not at all
- 1 hour or less
- 2-3 hours
- 4-6 hours
- More than 6 hours

In the last 24 hours have you vomited or thrown up?

- 7 times or more
- 5-6 times
- 3-4 times
- 1-2 times
- I did not throw up

In the last 24 hours how many times have you had retching or dry heaves without bringing anything up?

- No time
- 1-2 times
- 3-4 times
- 5-6 times
- 7 more times

4. General questions about health during pregnancy (Part 2).

Being pregnant and expecting a child can be intense and much can occur. We hope that you and the child you are expecting are well. If something has gone wrong during this pregnancy we would be grateful if you could tell us what has happened:

How do you rate your general state of health?

Very good; Good; Neither good or bad; Poor; Very poor

What pregnancy-week are you currently in?

When is your estimated date of delivery? _____

What is your weight today (kg)? _____

Are you expecting more than one child (twins, triplets etc.)? Yes/no/don't know

Comment: _____

Have you used antibiotics at any time during this pregnancy? Yes/no

If yes, at what week/weeks of pregnancy: _____

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you used antibiotics during this pregnancy?

- Respiratory tract infection (pneumonia, sinusitis)
- Tonsillitis
- Otitis
- Urinary tract infection
- Skin and soft tissue infection (skin, muscles, sore)
- Intestinal infection (bacteria, e.g. salmonella or campylobacter, parasites or traveller's diarrhoea)
- Abdominal infection (e.g. appendicitis, cholecystitis, diverticulitis)
- Gynaecological infection (e.g. chlamydia, gonorrhoea, bacterial vaginosis)
- Other: _____

Have you been to the dentist/dental hygienist so far during this pregnancy? Yes/no

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you been to the dentist/dental hygienist during this pregnancy? _____

Do you smoke/ use snus now?

If you smoke, how many cigarettes do you smoke a day? <1, 1-5, 6-10, >10

If you use snus, how many snus do you take a day? <1, 1-5, 6-10, >10

How often did you have a drink containing alcoholic DURING this pregnancy?

- Never
- Monthly or less
- 2 to 4 times a month
- 2 to 3 times a week
- 4 or more times a week

How many drinks containing alcohol do you have a typical day when you are drinking DURING this pregnancy?

- 1 or 2
- 3 or 4
- 5 or 6
- 7, 8 or 9
- 10 or more

So far during this pregnancy, do you have or have you had any complications/medical problems?

What pregnancy-related complications have you experienced during this pregnancy?

(Yes/no/don't know)

- Gestational diabetes
- Thyroid disease
 - o Overactive thyroid (hyperthyroidism)
 - o Underactive thyroid (hypothyroidism, treated with e.g. Levaxin)
- High blood pressure (hypertension) (that you did not have before pregnancy)
- Pre-eclampsia (toxaemia)
- Hyperemesis gravidarum (severe morning sickness)
- Depression
- Vaginal bleeding/threatened abortion
- Heartburn/dyspepsia
- Symphysis pubis dysfunction/pelvic girdle pain
- Other

If other, please describe which: _____

Do you take any medications regularly during this pregnancy? Yes/no

If yes, what medications do you take regularly during this pregnancy?

- Non-prescription/over-the-counter analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Alvedon, Ipren)
- Opioids, stronger analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Morfin, Oxynorm)
- Allergy medications (e.g. antihistamines like Aerius, Loratidin)
- Asthma medications (e.g. Inhalations like Bricanyl, Pulmicort, Ventoline)
- Antidepressant medications (e.g. Citalopram, Sertralin)
- Sedative and anti-anxiety agents (e.g. Sobril, Stesolid)
- Hypnotics/sleeping pills (e.g. Imovane, Propavan)
- Thyroid hormone (e.g. Levaxin)
- Antihypertensive/blood pressure medications (e.g. Enalapril, Furix, Lasix, Spironolacton, Amlodipin, Felodipin, Atacand, Losartan, Seloken, Metroprolol)
- Medications decreasing the gastric acid production (e.g. Proton-pump-inhibitors like Omeprazol or similar)
- Other

What other medications do you take regularly since you got pregnant? _____

In the last 24 hours, for how long have you felt nauseated or sick to your stomach?

- Not at all
- 1 hour or less
- 2-3 hours
- 4-6 hours
- More than 6 hours

In the last 24 hours have you vomited or thrown up?

- 7 times or more
- 5-6 times
- 3-4 times
- 1-2 times
- I did not throw up

In the last 24 hours how many times have you had retching or dry heaves without bringing anything up?

- No time
- 1-2 times
- 3-4 times
- 5-6 times
- 7 more times

5. General questions about health after pregnancy (Part 3)

Being pregnant and giving birth to a child can be intense and much can occur. We hope that you and your child are well. If something has gone wrong during this pregnancy or delivery we would be grateful if you could tell us what has happened:

How do you rate your general state of health?

Very good; Good; Neither good nor bad; Poor; Very poor

Questions about your delivery:

When was your child/children born (date of delivery)? _____

Did you give birth to one child or more? One child/ twins/triplets/other, comment _____

Did you have a boy or girl?

In what pregnancy-week were you when you delivered? _____

What was your weight at the end of your pregnancy before delivery (kg)? _____

What was the birth-weight of your child/children (g)? _____

How tall was your child/children at birth (cm)? _____

At delivery the child's well-being is graded at 1, 5 and 10 minutes after birth according to a special score called APGAR-score. The child can get 0-10 points. Do you remember what score your child/children got? Yes/no

If yes, what score did you child/children get at birth? _____

What presentation (position in the uterus) did your child have at delivery? Head first, breech position, shoulder first.

How did your delivery start? Spontaneously/induced/acute C-section before contractions/elective C-section before contractions.

If your delivery did not start spontaneously, why was induction/C-section performed? _____

How did your delivery finish, i.e. how was your child/children delivered? Vaginally without instruments/ vaginally, with instruments (e.g. forceps, vacuum delivery) /C-section

Did you receive antibiotics during delivery? Yes/no/don't know

Was your child/children healthy after delivery? Yes/no

If no, what happened? _____

Was your child/children healthy the first day after delivery? Yes/no

If no, what happened? _____

Did your child/children receive antibiotics in connection to or after the delivery?

Yes/no

If yes, when and for what reason? _____

Have you been able to breastfeed your child/children after delivery?

- No
- Yes, but stopped.
- Yes, still breastfeeding

Questions about the end of your pregnancy:

Have you been on sick-leave due to pregnancy? Yes/no

If yes, for what reason? _____

Have you used antibiotics at any time during this pregnancy? Yes/no

If yes, at what week/weeks of pregnancy: _____

Comment: _____

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you used antibiotics during this pregnancy?

- Respiratory tract infection (pneumonia, sinusitis)
- Tonsillitis
- Otitis
- Urinary tract infection
- Skin and soft tissue infection (skin, muscles, sore)
- Intestinal infection (bacteria, e.g. salmonella or campylobacter, parasites or traveller's diarrhoea)
- Abdominal infection (e.g. appendicitis, cholecystitis, diverticulitis)
- Gynaecological infection (e.g. chlamydia, gonorrhoea, bacterial vaginosis)
- Other: _____

Have you been to the dentist/dental hygienist during the last months of your pregnancy? Yes/no.

If yes, for what reason/reasons have you been to the dentist/ dental hygienist during the last months of your pregnancy? _____

Did you smoke/ use snus during the last months of your pregnancy? Yes/No

If you smoked, how many cigarettes did you smoke a day? <1, 1-5, 6-10, >10

If you used snus, how many snus did you take a day? <1, 1-5, 6-10, >10

How often did you have a drink containing alcoholic DURING the last months of this pregnancy?

- Never
- Monthly or less
- 2 to 4 times a month
- 2 to 3 times a week
- 4 or more times a week

How many drinks containing alcohol did you have a typical day when you were drinking DURING the last months of this pregnancy?

- 1 or 2
- 3 or 4
- 5 or 6
- 7, 8 or 9
- 10 or more

Do you have or did you have any pregnancy-related complications/ medical problems?

Yes/no/don't know

What pregnancy-related complications do you have or have had during this pregnancy? (Yes/no/don't know)

- Gestational diabetes
- Thyroid disease
 - o Overactive thyroid (hyperthyroidism)
 - o Underactive thyroid (hypothyroidism, treated with e.g. Levaxin)
- High blood pressure (hypertension) (that you did not have before pregnancy)
- Pre-eclampsia (toxaemia)
- Hyperemesis gravidarum (severe morning sickness)
- Depression
- Vaginal bleeding/threatened abortion
- Heartburn/dyspepsia
- Symphysis pubis dysfunction/ pelvic girdle pain
- Other

If other, please describe which; _____

Did you take any medications regularly during this pregnancy? Yes/no

If yes, what medications did you take regularly during the pregnancy?

- Non-prescription/over-the-counter analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Alvedon, Ipren)
- Opioids, stronger analgesics/painkillers (e.g. Morfin, Oxynorm)
- Allergy medications (e.g. antihistamines like Aeries, Loratidin)
- Asthma medications (e.g. Inhalations like Bricanyl, Pulmicort, Ventoline)
- Antidepressant medications (e.g. Citalopram, Sertralin)
- Sedative and antianxiety agents (e.g. Sobril, Stesolid)
- Hypnotics/sleeping pills (e.g. Imovane, Propavan)
- Thyroid hormone (e.g. Levaxin)
- Antihypertensive/blood pressure medications (e.g. Enalapril, Furix, Lasix, Spironolakton, Amlodipin, Felodipin, Atacand, Losartan, Seloken, Metroprolol)
- Medications decreasing the gastric acid production (e.g. Proton-pump-inhibitors like Omeprazol or similar)
- Other

What other medications do you take regularly during this pregnancy? _____

Throughout your whole pregnancy have you felt nauseated or sick to your stomach?

- Not at all
- 1 or more times
- 2-3 times
- 4-6 times
- More than 6 times

Throughout your whole pregnancy have you vomited or thrown up?

- 7 times or more
- 5-6 times
- 3-4 times
- 1-2 times
- I did not throw up

Throughout your whole pregnancy how many times have you had retching or dry heaves without bringing anything up?

- No time
- 1-2 times
- 3-4 times
- 5-6 times
- 7 or more times

6. Food and dietary supplements (Part 1)

Do you take iron supplements? Yes/no

Do you take other vitamin-, mineral or dietary supplements? Yes/no

What vitamin-, mineral- or dietary supplements do you take? _____

Have you during the last days consumed products containing probiotics (e.g. Proviva, Actimel) or dietary supplements (e.g. ProBi-mage or similar)?

No Yes, (please state which one of you know the name) _____

Are you vegetarian? Yes/no

Are you vegan? Yes/no

Do you eat fish? Yes/no

How often do you drink/eat one of the following?

Think about the last month.

	Daily	Several times a week	Once a week	More rarely than once a week
Sweet drinks with sugar (e.g. soda, juice)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sweet drinks without sugar (e.g. diet soda)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Multigrain bread	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fruit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vegetables /Root vegetables	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

7. Discomfort from the stomach (Part 1-2)

Have you in the last month experienced discomfort from: (Yes/no)

Diarrhoea?

Constipation?

Bloating/gases?

Other discomfort from stomach/intestines?

If yes, please describe: _____

What did your stool look like during the past two weeks? (see picture)

Tick all the boxes you have had. You can pick more than one alternative.

Type 1. Separate hard lumps, like nuts (hard to pass)

Type 2. Sausage shaped but lumpy.

Type 3. Like a sausage but with cracks in the surface

Type 4. Like a sausage or snake, smooth and soft.

Type 5. Soft blobs with clear-cut edges (easy to pass)

Type 6. Fluffy pieces with ragged edges, a mushy stool.

Type 7. Watery, no solid pieces, entirely liquid (diarrhoea).

8. Experienced stress (Part 1-2-3)

The following questions ask about your feelings and thoughts during the **past month**. In each question, you will be asked how often you felt or thought a certain way.

In the last month, how often have you been/felt:

	Never	Almost Never	Some-Times	Fairly Often	Very Often
a) Unable to control the important things in your life?	0	1	2	3	4
b) Confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	0	1	2	3	4
c) Things were going your way?	0	1	2	3	4
d) Difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	0	1	2	3	4

Please check the answer that comes closest to how you have felt in the past 7 days, not just how you feel today

- a) I have been able to laugh and see the funny side of things
- As much as I always could
 not quite so much now
 Definitely not so much now
 Not at all
- b) I have looked forward with enjoyment to things
- As much as I ever did
 Rather less than I used to
 Definitely less than I used to
 Hardly at all
- c) I have blamed myself unnecessarily when things went wrong
- Yes, most of the time
 Yes, some of the time
 Not very often
 No, never
- d) I have been anxious or worried for no good reason
- No, not at all
 Hardly ever
 Yes, sometimes
 Yes, very often
- e) I have felt scared or panicky for no very good reason
- Yes, quite a lot
 Yes, sometimes
 No, not much
 No, not at all

f) Things have been getting
on top of me

- Yes, most of the time I haven't been able to cope at all
- Yes sometimes I haven't been coping as well as usual
- No, most of the time I have coped quite well
- No, I have been coping as well as ever

g) I have been so unhappy
that I have had difficulty sleeping

- Yes, most of the time
- Yes, sometimes
- Not very often
- No, not at all

h) I have felt sad or miserable

- Yes, most of the time
- Yes, quite often
- Not very often
- No, not at all

i) I have been so unhappy
that I have been crying

- Yes, most of the time
- Yes, quite often
- Only occasionally
- No, never

j) The thought of harming myself
has occurred to me

- Yes, quite often
- Sometimes
- Hardly ever
- Never